

The acceptance of smart solutions on desalination plants

Kevin Colijn
Tilburg University
k.colijn@uvt.nl

Nick van Osch
Tilburg University
n.vanosch@uvt.nl

Jim Staring
Tilburg University
j.p.staring@uvt.nl

Mitchell Tiwon
Tilburg University
m.p.tiwon@uvt.nl

ABSTRACT

By 2025 at least half of the world's population will be living in water-stressed areas. Desalination, the process of the removal of salts and minerals from a target substance, is one of the solutions to counter freshwater scarcity. There are approximately 12500 desalination plants worldwide. But these plants are costly, both to build and to operate. Industry 4.0 offers new solutions to bring down costs and energy usage. But giving existing desalination plants a "smart" makeover is also costly. Thus, the purpose of this paper is to investigate the technology acceptance of smart desalination plants within water critical areas. An extended version of the technological acceptance (TAM) model with new variables is proposed. These variables are partly tested through two different types of data collection; interviews and surveys. More research is needed to validate the complete model. This paper contains the basis needed in order to conduct further research.

Keywords

Internet of Things, Smart Devices, Smart desalination plants, Water critical areas, Technology acceptance.

INTRODUCTION

With water being the core of all life on earth, one could argue that it is the most valuable product in the world. This makes it extremely worrying that by 2025, according to predictions made by the World Health Organization (WHO), at least half of the world's population will be living in water-stressed areas (World Health Organization, 2019). A prime example is Cape Town, the capital city of South Africa, which narrowly avoided a water crisis during an extreme drought in the summer of 2018 (D. Masante, 2018). Even though 71% of the earth is covered in water, less than 1% is readily available to be used by humans. Seen in this context, the limited and precious nature of freshwater becomes truly clear (Williams, 2014). Naturally, a multitude of

efforts are continuously being made in order to preserve the world's freshwater supply. These efforts are mainly focussed on cleaning polluted water and reducing waste in potable water. The advantages are that the costs are relatively low and pollution is being tackled at the source. However, the world's freshwater supply is still declining. This is where the desalination process comes into play. Water desalination plants can provide drinking water in areas where no natural supply of potable water exists. But these plants are costly, both to build and to operate (Ackerman, 2018). With the rise of Industry 4.0, new possibilities have arrived to bring down these costs and energy usage, known as smart desalination plants.

PROBLEM INDICATION

Desalination continues to grow due to increasing water scarcity in many parts of the world, consequently resulting in a rising number of water critical areas. All desalination processes have a negative effect on the environment due to their intensive consumption of energy and brine disposal, and are energy-intensive with a common minimum energy requirement (Al-Karaghoul and Kazmerski, 2013). Due to this intensive energy consumption, there is a need to make desalination plants and the accompanying desalination processes as energy-efficient as possible. This can be achieved by constructing smart desalination plants or by using smart solutions on existing desalination plants.

But to what extent is this solution important to local governments within water critical areas? Which factors impact their decision to opt for the smart desalination plants? Is sustainability at the top of the checklist for local governments that are in dire need of fresh water? Are the existing desalination plants capable to adopt a smart implementation? In this paper, research will be conducted on the technology acceptance of smart solutions on desalination plants within water critical areas. The findings of this research will be crucial for determining if smart solutions on desalination plants should be implemented in water critical areas.

RESEARCH QUESTION

To investigate the different influences on the adoption of smart desalination plants, the following research question has been formulated:

“Which variables affect the technology acceptance of smart solutions for existing desalination plants by local governments within water-critical areas?”

To answer the research question, the following theoretical sub questions have been formulated:

- What is defined as a water critical area?
- What is meant with smart solutions?
- Which external variables will be included in this research?
- What model will be used to test the technology acceptance?

THEORY

To investigate the different variables that affect the adoption of smart solutions on desalination plants, the following research question has been formulated:

“Which variables affect the technology acceptance of smart solutions for existing desalination plants by local governments within water-critical areas?”

To answer the research question, the following theoretical sub-questions have been formulated:

- What is defined as a water critical area?
- What is meant with smart solutions?
- Which external variables will be included in this research?
- What model will be used to test the technology acceptance?

Water critical areas

According to Pereira, Cordery, and Iacovos (2009), Water scarcity is among the main problems to be faced by many societies and countries in the world in the 21st century. Water scarcity is commonly defined as a situation when water availability in a country or region is below 1000m³/person/year. However, many regions and countries in the world experience much more severe scarcity, living with less than 500m³/person/year. To further demarcate this research, we define a water critical area as a country where water availability is below 1000m³/person/year.

Smart solutions

The term ‘smart’ is a broadly used definition, with a different context in research and everyday life. Teizer (2017) defines smart as self-monitoring analysis and reporting technology. In this research,

aimed at smart desalination plants, the term smart refers to a self-controlled system, which is monitored remotely from a control room and can adjust the valves automatically based on a variety of process variables. Additionally, the smart system gives insights into energy usage and is optimized to minimize the energy consumption of the plant (Cohen, 2009). This definition of smart solutions is in line with the highest level of smart solutions readiness for a plant, according to Lichtblau et al. (2015).

External variable 1: Smart solutions readiness

The smart solutions readiness is the level of readiness for implementing smart solutions within different dimensions of the organization. Schumacher, Erol and Sihm (2016) conducted research on existing Industry 4.0 readiness and maturity models. Readiness and maturity should not be confused with each other. The readiness assessment takes place before engaging in the maturing process whereas the maturity assessment focuses on capturing the as-it-is state whilst the maturing process.

After a careful examination of the five analyzed models in the research of Schumacher et al. (2016), it is concluded that the readiness model “IMPULS - Industry 4.0 Readiness” (Lichtblau et al., 2015) is the most suited readiness model for our research. The IMPULS - Industry 4.0 Readiness model is scientifically substantiated and the structure and results are clearly explained. The other four models offer fewer details regarding the development process, structure and assessment-methodology and therefore no base for detailed comparison. Additionally, the IMPULS - Industry 4.0 Readiness model is aimed at engineering plants, which is applicable to our research, whereas the other four models are focused on manufacturing companies.

The IMPULS - Industry 4.0 Readiness model represents the following dimensions: strategy and organization, smart factory, smart operations, smart products, data-driven services and employees of a desalination plant. These dimensions form the foundation for smart solution readiness. The smart solution readiness of a plant is divided into six levels, starting with level zero. Level zero describes the outsiders - those plants that have done nothing or very little to plan or implement smart solutions. Level five describes the top performers - those plants that have successfully implemented smart solutions. The characteristics of a top performer are listed in table 1.

Dimension:	Characteristics:
Strategy and organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy implemented and regularly reviewed • Enterprise-wide Industry 4.0 investments • Uniform, enterprise-wide innovation management established
Smart factory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment infrastructure already satisfies future functionalities • All data collected and used • Comprehensive IT system support of processes
Smart operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete system-integrated information sharing • Autonomous control and self-reacting processes implemented • Comprehensive IT security and cloud solutions implemented
Smart products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Products feature comprehensive add-on functionalities • Comprehensive use of collected data for various functions
Data-driven services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data-driven services through customer integration • Revenues generated from services (>10%) • High usage rate of data (>50% of collected data)
Employees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All skills available in several relevant areas

Table 1: Characteristics of a top performer per dimension.

External variable 2: Perceived net benefits

In this research, the term “perceived net benefits” is preferred because according to William H. Delone & Ephraim R. McLean (2003), the term “net benefits” arises from the original term “impacts” and these may be positive or negative. This may lead to possible confusion as to whether the results are “good” or “bad”. Also, the inclusion of “net” in “perceived net benefits” is important according to William H. Delone & Ephraim R. McLean (2003). This is because no single outcome is wholly positive, without any additional negative consequences. A.M. Adrian et al. (2005) state that the addition “perceived” is the belief that the technology will provide benefits of greater value than its costs. The term “perceived net benefit” is, therefore, the most accurate descriptor for this variable and therefore used in this research. The variable “perceived net benefits” is used as an umbrella term for the advantages and accompanying disadvantages that smart solutions on a desalination plant yields.

External variable 3: Sustainability

The term “sustainability” is broad and challenging to define precisely in its modern use. Originally, sustainability meant making only such use of renewable, natural resources that in the long term, can continue to be reliable to people (Sustainability Theories, 2019). Because sustainability is a broad term, delimitation is needed when determining which definition to apply to this research. The report of the Brundtland Commission (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987) describes

sustainability as having three co-equal elements or parts, all of which start (in English) with the letter e: equity, environment and economy. These three elements have formed the foundation for disaggregating and elaborating sustainability. Based on these three elements, six roots of sustainability can be identified. These six roots are defined by Portney (2015). Out of these six roots, the definition most suited for this research is defining sustainability from a carrying capacity. Portney argues that when viewing sustainability from a carrying capacity, it is often associated with maintaining earth’s carrying capacity, usually through the application of new and developing technologies to minimize the effect of individual or collective human behaviour.

However, maintaining earth’s carrying capacity is not well understood or agreed upon, and may be inconsistent with fundamental values that are prevalent in industrializing and industrialized countries. Robinson et al., (1990) suggest that “sustainability is defined as the persistence over an apparently indefinite future of certain necessary and desired characteristics of the socio-political system and its neutral environment”. In this context, maintaining the earth’s carrying capacity is mostly a function of the political and social values that prescribe and define human behaviours. Based on this, achieving sustainability requires types of socio-political characteristics and values rather than others.

External variable 4: Investment budget

The investment budget of a country is measured by the total value of the gross fixed capital formation

and changes in inventories and acquisitions less disposals of valuables for a unit or sector (The World Bank Group, 2019). Since a government can invest in different sectors (e.g. military weapons systems, public buildings) (OECD, 2019), this measurement of the investment budget is too broad for this research. To make the definition of the investment budget of a country more applicable for this research, the definition has been narrowed down to a countries' available amount of budget for drinking water.

TAM model

In order to make this research viable and important from a research perspective, we used the TAM model (Davis, 1989) to create an assessment model that can be used to test the acceptance of smart solutions within desalination plants. In the field of information systems, the technology acceptance model TAM is generally considered as the most common and influential theory of technology acceptance (Lee et al., 2003), and consequently received affluent empirical support. The theory of reasoned action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975) discusses how attitude impacts behaviour and forms the foundation on which the TAM is based. The TAM involves the two core predictors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use with the dependent variable: behaviour intention. Researchers have applied this model into several research streams after its introduction in 1989.

According to Davis (1989), the two core predictors of the TAM model, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, both aim at the users' experience of the new technology. This research aims to investigate whether local governments are willing to opt for smart solutions on desalination plants or not. Therefore, the definitions of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are not applicable for this research and have been adjusted

to fit within this research. The perceived usefulness can be interpreted as the perceived usefulness of the implementation of smart solutions on desalination plants as experienced by local governments. The perceived ease of use is replaced by the ease of transformation. The ease transformation entails the ease of transformation from the current level of readiness towards level five, a top performer.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The following conceptual model (figure 1) has been developed that provides a descriptive representation of the theory from this research. The aim is to create a theory that explains the relationships between the external variables and the two core predictors.

Hypotheses

- H1: The smart solutions readiness has a significant effect on the perceived net benefits.
- H2: The perceived net benefits have a significant effect on the perceived usefulness.
- H3: The country's investment budget has a significant effect on the country's view on sustainability.
- H4: The country's view on sustainability has a significant effect on the perceived usefulness.
- H5: The smart solutions readiness has a significant effect on the ease of transformation.

H1: The smart solutions readiness has a significant effect on the perceived net benefits.

Adrian et al. (2005) states that the perceived net benefits depend on the belief that the technology will provide benefits of greater value than its costs. The costs and accompanying benefits required for becoming a top performer depends on the current level of readiness (Lichtblau et al., 2015). Therefore it is expected that the smart solution readiness level

Figure 1: The conceptual model.

has a significant effect on the perceived net benefits.

H2: The perceived net benefits have a significant effect on the perceived usefulness.

The variable perceived net benefits is the belief that the technology will provide benefits of greater value than its costs (Adrian et al., 2005). No construct or method exists from past research that can quantify the net benefits of a smart desalination plant. Adrian et al. (2005) conducted a study that researches the variables that affect the intentions to adopt smart tools for precision agriculture. The results of this study show that the perceived net benefits directly affect perceived usefulness and intentions to adopt precision agriculture technologies. Therefore, it is expected that a government who perceived the potential positive net benefits of transforming to a smart desalination plant is more likely to adopt this smart solution than a government that does not perceive the net benefits of the smart solution.

H3: The country's investment budget has a significant effect on the country's view on sustainability.

The investment budget of a country is defined as the countries' available amount of budget for drinking water. The available investment budget for a country is expected to have a positive influence on a country's view on sustainability if the available budget increases. However, literature review shows that no prior research has been conducted on this expected correlation. Elliot (2004) states that "governance for sustainability is value-based acknowledging the fundamental importance of preservation of Earth's ecological integrity. There is little dispute that better governance is required. However, a precise definition of what this means or what it requires remains elusive." Therefore, the hypothesis has to be tested through research before conclusions can be drawn.

H4: The country's view on sustainability has a significant effect on the perceived usefulness.

Within the TAM model, the perceived usefulness is defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance" (Davis, 1989). Numerous researchers have since discovered that the TAM model yields consistently high explained variance for why users choose to utilize systems (Adams, Nelson & Todd, 1992; Mathieson, 1991; Thompson, Higgins & Howell, 1991). Within IS literature there is little explanation of the psychological origins of belief sets of perceived usefulness (Karahanna and Staub, 1999). The model aims to measure the effect of a country's view on sustainability on the perceived usefulness, from a psychological point of

view. This relates back to the socio-political values that were indicated to be of use when measuring sustainability, as mentioned in the theory chapter. By measuring these values, we suspect a direct effect between sustainability and perceived usefulness.

H5: The smart solutions readiness has a significant effect on the ease of transformation.

The perceived ease of transformation entails the ease of transformation from the current level of readiness towards level five, a top performer. These levels are based on the levels as formulated by Lichtblau et al. (2015). Therefore it is expected that the higher the level of smart solution readiness of a desalination plant, the higher the ease of the transformation to become a top performer will be, and vice versa.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research strategy

In order to research the correlation between the (external) variables within the conceptual model, multiple research strategies are required. Primary data will be gathered by conducting surveys and in-depth interviews. Secondary data will be gathered by conducting external archival research.

According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016) it is important to establish a good level of equivalence since this research is cross-national, Equivalence in research is divided into three parts. Namely construct, measurement and sample. With construct equivalence it is important to study the same phenomena in different countries, it is important to not only draw from the domestic literature but also from the country-specific literature when developing conceptualizations. With measurement equivalence, it is important to measure and study the phenomena in the same way in terms of wording and scaling. With sampling equivalence, it is important to achieve representative and comparable samples.

Data collection methods

Smart solutions readiness:

Data regarding the smart solutions readiness of a desalination plant will be gathered by conducting a questionnaire created by Lichtblau et al. (2015).

Investment budget:

Data regarding the investment budget will be gathered by conducting external archival research. The digital data is published by the WHO and UN-Water within the yearly Global Analysis and Assessment of Sanitation and Drinking-Water

(GLAAS) report (UN-Water & World Health Organization, 2019). The GLAAS report contains information regarding a countries' available budget for drinking water as part of the total expenditures in Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) per country.

Perceived net benefits:

Because prior theory is absent about the subject, exploratory research will be conducted in the form of an in-depth interview to gather an in-depth understanding about the net benefits with specialists in the field of producing desalination plants. With this in-depth interview, the aim is to collect and track down the net benefits of the smart solutions on desalination plants in the form of qualitative data. With these results, a survey will subsequently be conducted with a person in charge of the sustainability policy within the government of a country within a water critical area.

Sustainability:

As with the perceived net benefits, prior theory is absent. Therefore, an in-depth interview will be conducted. An in-depth interview allows the need for fewer participants to glean useful and relevant insights (Steber, 2017). The interview will be focused on the importance of sustainability in countries within a water critical area. The aim of the interview is to gain insight into the motives for countries to go for smart solutions.

Measurement

Smart solutions readiness:

The questionnaire by Lichtblau et al. (2015) measures the overall smart solutions readiness level on a scale of zero (outsider) to five (top performer). The results of this overall evaluation will be interpreted as follows: Level zero, outsider – very hard to transform; level one, beginner – hard to transform; level two, intermediate – neutral; level 3, experienced – easy to transform; level 4, expert – very easy to transform. level 5, top performer – no transformation required.

The weight of each dimension to calculate the overall smart solutions readiness level is distributed from a total of 100 points. The dimensions are weighted as follows: strategy and organization – 25.4; smart factory – 14.3; smart products – 18.5; data-driven services – 13.8; smart operations – 10.2; employees – 17.9. To measure the smart solutions readiness per dimension, a variety of scales are used.

Investment budget:

To measure the investment budget, the countries' expenditures in drinking water will be divided by the countries' total WASH expenditures. This ratio provides an indication of how much a country is willing to invest in drinking water. The ratio will be categorized in the following five categories: very unlikely, a ratio between 0.0-0.20; unlikely a ratio between 0.20-0.40; neutral, a ratio between 0.40-0.60; likely, a ration between 0.60-0.80; very likely, a ratio between 0.80-1.00.

Perceived net benefits:

In order to research the net benefits of smart solutions, an in-depth interview will be conducted with specialists in the field of producing desalination plants. The content of this interview will mainly focus on how the costs and yields of the smart solutions will weigh up against each other. The outcomes of the in-depth interview will provide the net benefits of smart solutions on a desalination plant in the form of qualitative data.

The outcomes of the prior interview will form input for the following. namely, with this data, another in-depth interview will be conducted with a government employee that has jurisdiction over sustainability decisions. The interviewee should have decision-making powers about desalination. This interview will measure the attitude towards perceived usefulness that depends on the perceived net benefits that have been quantified by the in-depth interview. The outcome of this interview will be unstructured qualitative data. The outcome and results will be analysed by thematic analysis with a six-step model as designed by Braun and Clark (2006). With these results, it is possible to form a conclusion over the correlation between the perceived net benefits and perceived usefulness.

Sustainability:

With the chosen and delimited definition of sustainability, socio-political characteristics and values should be measured in this interview. These outcomes and results will also be analysed using a thematic analysis. These values should reflect the stance on sustainability. These measurements then can be used to correlate the view on sustainability with the perceived usefulness of smart solutions for desalination plants.

Sampling

The population of this research are governments within water critical areas.

Smart solutions readiness:

By using judgment sampling, the experts of a desalination plant for each of the six dimensions of the smart solutions readiness model will be identified. These experts will come together in a focus group with a leading moderator, where the experts fill in the questionnaire together.

Investment budget:

The population consists of national governments that participated in the GLAAS 2019 survey. The survey was open to all interested countries, with a participation amount of 115 countries. A sample can be drawn out of this population. The sample frame is dependent on the country of the case study of the research.

Perceived net benefits and sustainability:

According to (DeLone & Mclean, 2003) the second issue of concern is to whom the net benefits are important. Different actors, players or stakeholders may have different opinions as to what constitutes a benefit to them. It is therefore important to narrow down the scope. Sampling for the variables perceived net benefits and sustainability is based on Robinson's (2013) approach for sampling in interview-based qualitative research. The sample universe consists out of government employees, that are employed in countries within water critical areas. This person functions as a proxy for a government or ministry that has jurisdiction over sustainability decisions. This means, that the interviewee should have executive, or decision-making, powers. The model its theory can be tested with a case. The case study design is a distinctive method that is separable from standard qualitative methods (Yin, 2009). It warrants a sample size of $N = 1$. Since the desired sample size is 1, a purposive sampling method has to be applied. In order to gain theoretical insight, intensity sampling is the preferred method of sampling (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Validity & reliability**Smart solutions readiness:**

The questionnaire by Lichtblau et al. (2015) used in this research is an off-the-shelf questionnaire. Sekaran and Bougie (2016) state that the use of off-the-shelf questionnaires increases the validity and reliability of the results.

Schumacher, Erol, and Sihm (2016) state it is important to stress that the questionnaire can only be answered properly if all respondents have a basic understanding of the concepts of Industry 4.0. To ensure the focus group has a basic understanding of

the concepts of smart solutions, they will get a brief update regarding smart solutions at the start of the session.

Investment budget:

By using the GLAAS (2019) report the validity and reliability have been increased. The review process for the GLAAS data collection has been strengthened for clarifying and confirming country data through a multistep process (UN-Water & World Health Organization, 2019). The multistep process has significantly enhanced the quality of the collected data, compared to previous cycles.

Additionally, external validation of the GLAAS country survey data was conducted with experts on WASH from selected sample countries. An expert on WASH could only participate if he did not participate in the multistep process and has demonstrated knowledge and experience of the WASH sector in the country.

Perceived net benefits and sustainability:

To further enhance the validity it is important to prevent the use of loaded questions where the personal opinions of the researchers on the subjects become clear. Since the model is theory testing, there is a strong justification for $N = 1$ in case-specific research (Festinger, Riecken & Schacter, 1956). It is also important to note that the interviewee needs to have a deep understanding of the subject. Finally, it is important to prevent biases from both the interviewer as the interviewee.

DATA ANALYSIS**Smart solutions readiness:**

The gathered data from the questionnaire will be processed by using the online Industry 4.0 Readiness check for businesses. This online tool analyzes the gathered data and presents the results of the survey. The outcome of the overall smart solutions readiness level will be used to indicate the effect of the smart solutions readiness on the perceived net benefits and perceived ease of transformation.

Investment budget:

The investment budget of a country requires will be directly interpreted from the GLAAS 2019 report. Based on the investment budget, the country will be categorized, which leads to an indication of the country's willingness to invest.

Perceived net benefits and sustainability:

Thematic analysis is one of the most common and effective methods to analyse interview data. When done correctly, it also has high traceability and verification making it a trustworthy method (Nowell, Norris, White & Moules, 2017). The six main steps (figure 2) of a thematic analysis will be conducted, as designed by Braun and Clark (2006).

RESULTS

Smart solutions readiness:

Due to the small time frame of this research, a case study has not been conducted. To show the practicability of the questionnaire, a dummy questionnaire has been filled in. The overall evaluation shows the dummy desalination plant has a smart solution readiness level of 1, shown in figure 3.

Investment budget:

To demonstrate the interpretation of the GLAAS (2019) report data, Nigeria is picked as an example. The investment budget of Nigeria is 0.84, based on the data of the GLAAS (2019) report, shown in table 2.

Perceived net benefits and sustainability:

To gather data about the net benefits, specialists from Siemens were approached. Mr Meisel, who is a specialist in the field of chemical engineering stated that due to the complexity of the topic it is very difficult to objectively compare such values in distinctive numbers. Therefore, in this research, it is not feasible to quantify the net benefits of smart solutions by weighing the costs against the yields.

As a result of this setback and due to the time and budget constraints of this research, a qualitative interview about the perceived net benefits and

Phase	Description of the process
1. Familiarizing yourself with your data:	Transcribing data (if necessary), reading and re-reading the data, noting down initial ideas.
2. Generating initial codes:	Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code.
3. Searching for themes:	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme.
4. Reviewing themes:	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts (Level 1) and the entire data set (Level 2), generating a thematic 'map' of the analysis.
5. Defining and naming themes:	Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme, and the overall story the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
6. Producing the report:	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis.

Figure 2: The six main steps of a thematic analysis.

Figure 3: The overall evaluation of a dummy smart desalination plant.

Government WASH budget (US\$ millions, constant 2017 US\$)		Annual WASH expenditure (US\$ millions, constant 2017 US\$)					Ratio
National		By subsector					
Country	Year	Budget	Drinking-water	Sanitation	Hygiene	Other	
Nigeria	2018	55.7	46.8	8.9	0.0	0.0	0.84

Table 2: The interpretation of the GLAAS (2019) report data.

sustainability with the government employee that has jurisdiction over desalination and sustainability is not feasible. With this knowledge, it is therefore not possible to form a conclusion on the correlation between these variables.

Using the results for the hypothesis gives us the following:

H1: The smart solutions readiness has a significant effect on the perceived net benefits.

The dummy desalination plant has a current smart solutions readiness of level one, beginner. Therefore, the expected benefits by a transformation to a level five, top performer, will be high. However, the accompanying costs of the transformation to a level five, top performer, are yet to be determined. Without insight into the costs, the effect of the smart solutions readiness on the perceived net benefits can not be tested.

H2: The perceived net benefits have a significant effect on the perceived usefulness.

Meisel, the expert from Siemens, indicated that further research is necessary in order to conclusively give answer to this hypothesis. He did not however, disprove the correlation between the perceived net benefits and perceived usefulness.

H3: The country's investment budget has a significant effect on the country's view on sustainability.

Nigeria's investment budget of 0.84 indicates it is very likely that they will invest in drinking water. The suspected correlation between a country its investment budget and a country its view on sustainability however, has to be measured through the interview. The researcher then can investigate whether the investment budget has a correlation with the view on sustainability.

H4: The country's view on sustainability has a significant effect on the perceived usefulness.

This hypothesis can only be concluded once the interview actually has taken place. As of now, the hypothesis is neither proven nor unproven.

H5: The smart solutions readiness has a significant effect on the ease of transformation.

The dummy desalination plant has a current smart solutions readiness of level one, beginner. This indicates it will be hard to transform the current dummy desalination plant to a top performer desalination plant. This shows the significance of the current smart solutions readiness of the desalination plant on the ease of transformation.

DISCUSSION

The main purpose of this research was to examine which variables affect the technology acceptance of smart solutions for existing desalination plants by local governments within water-critical areas. The external variables that were researched are: smart solutions readiness, perceived net benefits, sustainability, investment budget. Due to the lack of available data as a result of the time constraints of this research, the hypotheses have not been tested. However, a dummy questionnaire has been conducted and shows the practicability of the questionnaire and its outcome. Hence, the theory has partially been tested but not proven. Next to this, Nigeria has been picked as an example to show the practicability of conducting archival research and interpreting the outcome. In order to develop a grounded theory about the conceptual model and the accompanying hypotheses, further research is needed.

CONCLUSION

Since this research focuses on countries within water critical areas and has a time constraint, it is not feasible to conduct qualitative and reliable interviews in these countries. Therefore this research is mostly dependent on archival research to gather data over these particular countries.

Since the participation in the WASH research was voluntary, not all countries in the world participated. This leads to a limitation in the population frame.

As a result of this setback and due to the time and budget constraints of this research, a qualitative interview with the government employee that has jurisdiction over desalination and sustainability is not feasible. Further research is therefore needed to gather these results to form a conclusion about the accompanying hypothesis.

This research is not conducted on an existing desalination plant in countries within a water critical area, but with the use of archival research and a dummy desalination plant.

In order to make this research viable and important from a research perspective, we used the TAM model to create an assessment model that can be used to test the acceptance of smart solutions in other industries. Future research should test the conceptual model with legitimate data to prove the usability of the conceptual model. When the usability of the conceptual model is proven, the model can be eventually be applied to different sectors to test the acceptance of smart solutions by local governments. Additionally, future research needs to be conducted to test other variables that might affect the acceptance of smart solutions on a desalination plant.

REFERENCES

- Adams, D., Nelson, R., & Todd, P. (1992). Perceived usefulness, ease of use, and usage of information technology: a replication. *MIS Quarterly*, 16(2), 227-247.
- Adrian, A.M., Norwood, S.H., & Mask, P.L. (2005). Producers' perceptions and attitudes toward precision agriculture technologies. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 48, 256-271.
- Ajzen, I. (1991) The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behavior & Human Decision Processes*, 50(2),179-211.
- Al-Karaghoul, A., & Kazmerski, L.L. (2013). Energy consumption and water production cost of conventional and renewable-energy-powered desalination processes. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 24, 343-356.
- Cohen, Y. (2009). UCLA develops 'smart' water desalination system. *Membrane Technology*, 11, 8-8.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340.
- Delone, W.H., & McLean, E.R. (2003). The DeLone and McLean model of information systems success: A ten-year update. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 19(4), 9-30, doi: 10.1080/07421222.2003.11045748
- Elliot, L. (2004). *The global politics of the environment*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Festinger, L., Riecken, H.W., & Schacter, S. (1956) *When Prophecy fails: a social and psychological study of a modern group that predicted the end of the world*. Minneapolis: University of Minneapolis Press.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Lee, Y., Kozar, K.A., & Larsen, K.R.T. (2003). The Technology Acceptance Model: Past, Present, and the Future. *Communications of Association for Information Systems*, 12(50), 752-780.
- Lichtblau, K., Stich, V., Bertenrath, R., Blum, M., Bleider, M., Millack, A., ...Schröter, M. (2015). *Industrie 4.0 Readiness*. VMDA [case study]
- Mathieson, K. (1991). Predicting user intentions: comparing the technology acceptance model with the theory of planned behavior. *Information Systems Research*, 2(3), 173-191.
- Miles, M.B., & Huberman, A.M. *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*. London: Sage.
- Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E., & Moules, N. J. (2017). Thematic Analysis: Striving to Meet the Trustworthiness Criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16(1). doi: 10.1177/1609406917733847
- OECD (2019), Gross domestic product (GDP) (indicator). doi: 10.1787/dc2f7aec-en
- Pereira, L.S., Cordery, I., & Iacovides, I. (2009). *Coping with water scarcity: Addressing the challenges*. [e-reader version]. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4020-9579-5.
- Portney, K.E. (2015). *Sustainability* [e-reader version]. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/uvtilburg-ebooks/detail.action?docID=4397950>
- Schumacher, A., Erol, S., & Sihn, W. (2016). A Maturity Model for Assessing Industry 4.0 Readiness and Maturity of Manufacturing Enterprises. *Procedia CIRP*, 52. 161-166.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons.
- Teizer, J. (2015). Wearable, wireless identification sensing platform: Self-monitoring alert and reporting technology for hazard avoidance and training (SmartHat). *ITcon*, 20, 295-312
- The World Bank Group (2019), Gross capital formation (% of GDP). Retrieved from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ne.gdi.totl.zs>
- Thompson, R.L., Higgings, C.A. & Howell, J.M. (1991). Personal computing: toward a conceptual model of utilization. *MIS Quarterly*, 15(1), 125-143.
- UN-Water, & World Health Organization. (2019). *National systems to support drinking-water, sanitation and hygiene: Global status report 2019*. Geneva: World Health Organization. Retrieved from <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/326444/9789241516297-eng.pdf?ua=1>
- World Commission on Environment and Development (1987). *Our Common Future*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. p.27.
- Yin, R.K. (2009). *Case study research: design and methods*. London: Sage.